

Defining the optimal imaging time point for fluorescence-lifetime-based tumor identification using the non-targeting near-infrared dye indocyanine green and post-processed high-dynamic-range images

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Abstract: Indocyanine green (ICG) is used for tumor visualization using fluorescence-intensity imaging, but false-positive signals are common. Fluorescence-lifetime-based tumor identification may overcome this limitation by measuring the time behavior of fluorescent light. However, the optimal time point for fluorescence lifetime imaging after the intravenous administration of ICG is yet to be defined. In this paper, the *in vivo* time course of ICG is investigated in syngeneic tumor-bearing mice using a novel macroscopic fluorescence lifetime camera. High-dynamic-range images were generated through post-processing, investigated, and subsequently applied for time-domain intensity and lifetime image analysis. The results indicate that fluorescence lifetime imaging may provide higher accuracy in tumor identification than intensity-based imaging, but the optimal imaging time point appears to require a 24–48 hour interval after intravenous injection, similar to intensity measurements. However, earlier time points might be of interest to investigate for liver and intestinal tumors.

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1. Introduction

Fluorescence lifetime (FL) measurements capture the average time a fluorophore remains in its excited state following excitation with light that matches the fluorophore's absorption spectrum [1]. Since the FL of a fluorophore can be sensitive to its direct surrounding molecular environment, FL imaging (FLI) offers opportunities to discriminate pathologic from healthy tissue based on their distinct molecular landscapes and metabolic signatures [2–4]. So far, most studies were conducted in the field of FLI microscopy (FLIM) [1,3,4]. However, thanks to recent advances FLI has expanded its application beyond the microscopic scale, including highly sensitive and fast macroscopic wide-field imaging systems, miniaturized and fiber-based implementations, and rapid or fit-free analysis methods [5–9]. Macroscopic studies allow for the non-invasive visualization of lifetime maps across whole-body small animal imaging models, *ex vivo* specimens,

and intra-operatively defined tissue affected by disease [7,9–13]. Consequently, FLI of intrinsic fluorophores has been leveraged to visualize and identify tumor tissue, atherosclerotic plaques, ischemic injury, inflammatory lesions, or fibrotic tissue [8,12,14–17]. However, given the limited penetration depth of endogenous autofluorescence ($\approx 200\text{--}300\ \mu\text{m}$), the use of exogenous contrast agents has been proposed, particularly those in the near-infrared (NIR) window [7,12]. The clinically approved dye indocyanine green (ICG) is particularly of interest as it is already under investigation for intra-operative cancer margin assessment using fluorescence intensity (FI) measurements in veterinary and human clinical trials [18–21]. In those clinical studies, ICG is typically administered 24–48 hours (h) prior to surgery at doses of 0.5 to 5 mg/kg to achieve an adequate tumor-to-background ratio (TBR) [18–20,22]. Nevertheless, due to its non-targeted nature, ICG also accumulates in inflamed tissue, which shares similar vascular permeability characteristics with tumors [23,24]. As a result, FI imaging alone cannot be used for reliable tumor delineation in the presence of inflammatory tissue, limiting the specificity of ICG-based FI-guided surgery [25,26]. Alternatively, *ex vivo* studies on veterinary and human tumor specimens demonstrated that FLI of ICG provides additional insight and may improve tumor delineation accuracy compared to FI measurements alone [7,27].

Because FL values depend on the molecular environment of the fluorophore rather than its concentration, the optimal imaging time point for FL-based tumor identification with ICG might differ from that used for FI imaging. Using the novel, in-house developed, time-gated *tauCAM* camera, which surpasses traditional intensified charge-coupled device cameras in quantum efficiency for NIR detection, and implements gating directly at the pixel level [28], we investigated the *in vivo* time-course of ICG in two mouse models bearing syngeneic tumor types. Similarities and discrepancies between FI and FL values are discussed.

Furthermore, we explored the use of high dynamic range (HDR) measurements to improve the accuracy of time-domain FI and FL image analysis. Since FL measurements are governed by a fluorescent decay that spans a large dynamic range, the camera sensor should reliably capture this range across time-gates and pixels, without saturating at high intensities or losing accuracy at low intensities. However, their distribution is typically larger than the linear range of the imaging system [28,29]. In the absence of multi-exposure HDR imaging, defining the optimal acquisition time for accurate FI and FL image analysis in the time-domain can be challenging [28]. For this reason, post-processed HDR images were generated and investigated for more robust time-domain FI and FL image analysis.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Macroscopic fluorescent lifetime imaging system

The macroscopic FLI system consists of a novel sub-nanosecond time-gated camera (*tauCAM*) based on a 128×128 -pixel current-assisted photonic sampler image sensor. The camera is synchronized to a 775 nm (bandwidth below 1 nm) 40 MHz pulsed laser (Katana HP, NKT photonics, Birkerød, Denmark). Specifications on sensitivity, linearity and crosstalk of the imaging system have been described previously [28]. A built-in filter mount enables the manual exchange of optical filters. Before each experiment, the neutral density (ND) filter (NE30B-A OD3, Thorlabs, Newton, NJ, USA) was placed in front of the lens to measure the instrument response function (IRF). Thereafter, an 835 nm BrightLine bandpass filter (FF01-835/70-25, Semrock, West Henrietta, New York, USA) was placed in front of the lens to measure the fluorescent emission of ICG. The *tauCAM* is operated from a custom-made software delivered with the imaging system.

2.2. Fluorescent phantoms

The backside of an ICG-equivalent phantom (ICG-DT02 RFD001, Quel imaging, Vermont, USA), which consists of a uniform 6.1×6.1 cm surface, was used to verify the influence of image acquisition time on FI and FL measurements. To evaluate the effect of light (dark versus room light) on the calculation of FI and FL values, three wells of a custom-built epoxy phantom were filled with ICG at a concentration of 256, 512 or 1024 nM [30].

2.3. Animal models

All *in vivo* procedures were approved by the Ethical Commission for Animal Experimentation at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel and carried out in compliance with the Belgian regulations and EU Directive 2010/63/EU (project number 22-272-23). Three female Balb/c and three female C57Bl/6J mice (Charles River Laboratories, l'Abresle, France) were housed in individual ventilated cages ($n = 3$ mice/cage) in 40-60% humidity with a light/dark cycle of 14/10 h. Mice received standard diet (SAFE 105, Safe Diet, Augy, France) and water *ad libitum*. Balb/c mice were subcutaneously inoculated with syngeneic 4T1 breast cancer cells (1×10^6 cells in 150 μ L phosphate buffered saline (PBS); ATCC), whereas C57Bl/6J mice were subcutaneously inoculated with syngeneic MC38 colon cancer cells (1×10^6 cells in 150 μ L PBS; ATCC) at the level of the hip on the right hind leg. Following inoculation, mice were monitored once a day to identify potential changes in behavior, body condition score, and physical appearance. Every 2-3 days, subcutaneous tumors were measured with a digital caliper and mice were weighted. Tumors exceeding 1500 mm³, severe tumor ulceration, weight loss equal to or higher than 20% compared to the day of tumor inoculation, severely impacted mobility and abnormal posture/behavior were considered humane endpoints.

During experiments, mice were anesthetized with isoflurane (5% for induction, 2% for maintenance, 1.5 L/min oxygen flow rate) and positioned in left *lateral*- and *dorsal decubitus* on black non-reflecting paper with room lights on. Mice were shaved and baseline images were acquired prior to injection of ICG to assess for possible tissue autofluorescence. Thereafter, mice were intravenously (iv) injected via the lateral tail vein with a 5 mg/kg dose of ICG (Diagnostic Green GmbH, Belgium) diluted in *aqua ad injectabilia* (B. Braun, Machelen, Belgium). Images were obtained at 1 h, 6 h, 24 h, and 48 h post-injection (pi) with room lights on. Between imaging time points mice were taken off isoflurane and permitted to recover until the next imaging time point. Following *in vivo* measurements all mice were euthanized by cervical dislocation under isoflurane anesthesia. An incision was made along the *linea alba* to locate residual fluorescence in the abdomen *in situ*. Thereafter, major organs (liver, stomach, intestines, kidneys) and tumors with surrounding tissue were collected and fixed in 4% formalin for 12 h. After those 12 h, tissues were stored in PBS at 4⁰C until paraffin-embedding the next day or over the weekend. Paraffin blocks remained at 4⁰C for 2 weeks post-embedding. *Ex vivo* tissues, before formalin fixation, and formalin-fixed-paraffin embedded (FFPE) tissues were imaged as described above. Tissues of the remaining 2/3 Balb/c mice were frozen as back-up.

2.4. Image acquisition and data processing

For all experiments, the height of the imaging system was set to 15 cm above the imaging table, with a field of view of 7.4×7.4 cm resulting in a spatial resolution of 1.12 lp/mm. Experiments performed with the ICG-equivalent phantom were conducted in the dark with a laser output of 100 mW (1.8 mW/cm²) and acquisition times ranging from 1 to 20 ms, with 1 ms steps. For the epoxy phantom, imaging was conducted in the dark and with room lights on, using a laser output of 800 mW and an acquisition time of 5 ms. For all experiments in mice, imaging was conducted with room lights on and a laser output of 800 mW (14.6 mW/cm²). *In vivo* and *ex vivo* images were acquired with acquisition times ranging from 5 ms to 25 ms in steps of 5 ms, 25 ms to 100 ms in steps of 25 ms and 100 ms to 200 ms in steps of 50 ms. Since the measurements were

recorded with sequential acquisitions, imaging took up to 5 minutes per side. Paraffin blocks were imaged with acquisition times of 100 ms, 150 ms and 200 ms.

At the start of each experiment, the IRF was determined based on reflectance measurements through the ND filter using a white piece of paper. Thereafter the ND filter was replaced by the emission filter for time-gated FI and FL measurements. For each image acquisition time, 128 frames were acquired and combined into an image cube. The image cube contains a brightfield image at frame 0 followed by 127 frames representing the temporal decay; a 4 ns gate width and 100 ps spacing between frames were used. From each image cube, an FI image was generated by extracting the decay peak FI value in each pixel. The FL image was obtained by applying a pixel-wise mono-exponential curve fit with the IRF included in the fitting model. Since the τ_{CAM} has a linear range up to 15000 AU [28], this value was set as the maximum threshold for FL computation. In addition a lower threshold of 1000 AU was applied. Therefore, only pixels with decay peak FI values between 1000-15000 AU were considered valid for FL computation. For some acquisition times, motion (due to breathing) was detected at the level of the intestines. These images were discarded for lifetime computation. To determine the impact of including all pixels versus valid pixels only for the calculation of an average FL value, the FL value was plotted against the FI value per acquisition time. A standard deviation plot was included to reveal variability and therefore accuracy of the average FL value. A valid pixel percentage was calculated on each image per acquisition time by dividing the number of pixels with decay peak values in the range of 1000-15000 AU with the total number of pixels in the ROI multiplied by 100. Furthermore, the valid pixel percentage was plotted against the standard deviation plot to define the number of valid pixels required in a chosen ROI for reliable average FL calculations. Since FI values can cover a very large range in an image, both invalid and valid pixels are often present in the full image. Therefore, HDR image cubes were generated through the post-processing of our image cubes: image cubes of the same time point but varying acquisition times were combined. Each pixel in the HDR image cube received the fluorescent curve of the acquisition time in which the decay peak contained the highest FI value, in the range of 1000-15000 AU. An HDR_{all} FL image cube was generated containing all acquisition times, whereas an HDR_{n=2} FL image cube was generated containing only the 10 ms and 100 ms acquisition times. From the generated HDR FL image cubes, an HDR FI cube was also derived. Since HDR image cubes for lifetime calculation were generated using only FI values in the range of 1000-15000 AU, so in the linear range, the HDR intensity image cube was generated by rescaling the intensity values with the acquisition time from which the decay was derived and multiplying the resulting values by 200 (i.e. highest acquisition time) to ensure sufficient intensity values for FI calculation at all time points. The valid pixel percentage for FL calculation was presented in a 3-color-coded image of which the colors orange, green and red refer to invalid pixels with decay peak FI values below 1000 AU, valid pixels and invalid pixels with decay peak FI values above 15000 AU, respectively.

2.5. Data analysis

In Fiji (ImageJ 1.54P, NIH, USA), ROIs were drawn based on the brightfield images. An ROI was drawn over the entire backside of the ICG-equivalent phantom and over each well in the custom-built epoxy phantom. In mice, ROIs were defined based on the outlines of the macroscopically visible tumor and surrounding tissue in left *lateral decubitus*. Additionally, in mice, ROIs were drawn at the level of the liver and intestines where off-target uptake of ICG was observed. The ROIs of liver and intestinal tissue were drawn based on FI signal present in *dorsal decubitus*. Median intensity values were calculated to represent the linear behavior of fluorescence over various acquisition time except when TBRs were involved. For those and all other measurements, average FI and FL values were used. Histograms depicting the normalized distribution within each ROI, in function of the measured FI or FL values, were generated in GraphPad Prism (GraphPad Software 10.5.0, Boston, MA, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Influence of image acquisition conditions on intensity and lifetime measurements

First, we investigated the effect of the image acquisition time on FI and FL measurements, in the ICG-equivalent flatfield phantom. A linear increase in median FI values was observed with increasing acquisition time until saturation (>15000 AU) occurred in least 20% of ROI pixels (Fig. 1(a),(b)). Saturated pixels were excluded. Accordingly, the number of valid pixels that could be used for lifetime computation decreased at those higher acquisition times (Fig. 1(b)). Pixels with decay peak FI values below 1000 AU (thus at low acquisition times) were also considered

Fig. 1. Influence of image acquisition time on fluorescence intensity (FI) and fluorescence lifetime (FL) measurements. In the phantom, FI (■) values increased linearly with increasing acquisition time (a) until saturation occurred in at least 20% of ROI pixels; reflected by a valid pixel percentage below 80% (●) (a,b). In contrast, the average fluorescence lifetime (FL) value (●) remained relatively stable (a). However, this was only true when the average FL value was calculated with valid pixels only (i.e., pixels with decay peak FI values in the threshold range of 1000-15000 AU) (●). When pixels beyond this range were included, average FL values deviated at very short and large acquisition times (●) compared to when only valid pixels were included (●) (a). This was reflected by a higher standard deviation (●) at very short and large acquisition times compared to the standard deviation with valid pixels only (●) (b). Similar results were observed *in vivo* in Balb/c (c,d) and C57Bl/6J mice (e,f). ROIs are represented in grey.

invalid since their fluorescent curves were of insufficient quality. Therefore, the valid pixel percentage for FL calculation also declined at low acquisition times (Fig. 1(b)). The decreased accuracy resulting from the decreased valid pixel percentage was reflected by a higher standard deviation for FL measurements (b). Indeed, when invalid ROI pixels were included, a higher standard deviation and altered average FL value were observed at very short (1-2 ms) and long (>14 ms) acquisition times (Fig. 1(a),(b)). In contrast, when only valid pixels were included, the average FL value remained constant over multiple acquisition times with consistent accuracy (Fig. 1(a),(b)). The higher standard deviation observed at very short acquisition times (1-2 ms) is attributed to the inhomogeneity of the phantom (Supplement 1, Fig. S1).

Consistent with the phantom study, similar *in vivo* findings were obtained in the tumor ROIs of 4T1 (Balb/c) and MC38 (C57BL/6J) tumor-bearing mice, imaged 24 h pi of ICG (Fig. 1(c)-(f)). *In vivo*, FI values also increased linearly with increasing acquisition time while the average FL value remained constant; provided the FL value was calculated with valid pixels only and the ROI contained a valid pixel percentage of at least 70%.

Next, we investigated the effect of room light conditions on FI- and FL measurements. Small deviations (-5.53% \rightarrow +12.58%) in average intensity values were observed between measurements conducted in the dark and with room lights on. In contrast, barely any difference was observed between imaging conditions using FLI (-0.53% \rightarrow +0.57%) (Supplement 1, Fig. S2). Therefore, all subsequent experiments were conducted with room lights on.

3.2. High-dynamic-range images applied through post-processing

Because fluorescent decays are exponential in nature, the total dynamic range of an FLI image cube can be larger than the linear range of the image sensor [28]. This can make it challenging to determine the most appropriate acquisition time for accurate FI and FL image analysis. Since average FL values computed with valid pixels only were considered relatively independent of the chosen acquisition time (Fig. 1(a)-(f)), we investigated the use of HDR measurements through the post-processing of our non-HDR FL image cubes.

The HDR image cube combines fluorescent decays from multiple acquisition times to ensure every pixel has sufficient signal for lifetime computation, while preventing saturation (Fig. 2(a)). The resulting HDR image yields a 100% valid pixel count for FI and FL measurements (Fig. 2(a)-(b)). The HDR image provides the same FL distributions as a non-HDR image, depicted on overlaying histograms representing pixel-by-pixel FL values from the tumor ROI of a 4T1-tumor bearing Balb/c mouse (Fig. 2(b)-(c)). Notably, an HDR image can be created from as few as two image cubes ($\text{HDR}_{n=2}$). To illustrate this concept, Fig. 2(b) shows an HDR image being generated from as few as two image cubes ($\text{HDR}_{n=2}$). This approach is valid provided that their combination results in a 100% valid pixel coverage across the entire field of view, as is the case for the 10 ms and 100 ms acquisition times. This produces results equivalent to those obtained using all available acquisition times together (HDR_{all}) (Fig. 2(b)).

HDR FI images allow to compare HDR FL distributions with FI distributions per time point or over time with multiple time points under investigation (Fig. 2(b), 3(a), 3(e)). Since HDR FI images are divided by their acquisition time and multiplied by a scaling factor, FI calculations can be made without the need to check images for noise or saturation when comparing TBRs over time (Supplement 1, Fig. S3). The HDR FI images also provide the same FI distributions as a non-HDR FI image in which a 100% valid pixel count is observed (Fig. 3(b); Supplement 1, Fig. S3).

3.3. *In vivo* time-course of ICG by HDR intensity and HDR lifetime images

Next, the *in vivo* time-course of ICG was investigated in two syngeneic mouse tumor-models, using HDR_{all} FI and HDR_{all} FL images. An overview of the *in vivo* and *ex vivo* FI and FL values can be found in Supplement 1 Table 1-2. At 1 h pi, high FI values were observed at

Fig. 2. The combination of time-domain image cubes of varying acquisition times into high-dynamic range (HDR) image cubes. In the HDR image cube, pixels get the fluorescent decay from the acquisition time where the pixel has the highest decay peak FI value in the range of 1000-15000 AU (a). From the HDR image cube a brightfield image, image showing pixel validity, FI image and FL image could be derived (a). A minimum of two image cubes was needed for HDR measurements: similar results were obtained when all acquisition times were included for post-processing (HDR_{all}) as when only two acquisition times (10 ms, 100 ms) were included (HDR_{n=2}) (b). The HDR FI and HDR FL images provided similar FI and FL distributions as non-HDR images where a 100% valid pixel count was observed in the tumor ROI (50 ms) (b). Overlaying histograms of the tumor from the 50 ms image and ‘HDR_{all}’ and ‘HDR_{n=2}’ image revealed similar FL distributions and average FL values as the non-HDR 50 ms lifetime image with a 100% valid pixel count in the tumor ROI, depicted on histograms representing pixel by pixel FL distributions in the tumor ROI (c).

Fig. 3. Representative brightfield, HDR_{all} FI and HDR_{all} FL images of immune-competent Balb/c mice (a) and immune-competent C57Bl/6J mice with subcutaneous breast cancer (4T1) (a) and colon carcinoma (MC38) tumors, respectively (e), imaged over multiple time points (1 h, 6 h, 24 h, 48 h and *ex vivo*). On the brightfield images *in vivo*, the ROIs that were used to calculate average FI and FL values of the tumor (T) and surrounding tissue (St) are indicated in dark and light blue, respectively. The same ROIs are outlined on the *ex vivo* brightfield image, with additional ROIs for the stomach, intestinal tissue, liver and kidneys. Scatter dot plots show average FI (b, f) and FL values (c, g) over time while histograms depict the distributions of lifetime values per time point, with average FL differences of 80-100ps between tumor and surrounding tissue by 24 h pi (d, h); * In the absence of autofluorescence HDR measurements, values are represented on a non-HDR image of 100 ms. ** Because images were not conducted in left lateral decubitus for C57Bl/6J mice, the autofluorescence image of the C57Bl/6J mouse is represented in ventral decubitus. *Legend colors plots intensity/lifetime over time and histograms:* ● Tumor, ● Surrounding tissue, ● Liver, ● Intestines, ● Tumor-to-background ratio. T: tumor, St: surrounding tissue, Sto: stomach, Int: intestines, Li: liver, Ki: kidney.

the level of the intestines, in both mouse strains, while moderate to high signal was observed in the tumor and surrounding tissue (Fig. 3(a)-(b), 3(e-f)). While in normal tissue, average FI values rapidly decreased, this decrease was slower in the tumor, leading to increased TBRs over time (Fig. 3(b), 3(f)). However, different trends were observed with FL measurements. At 1 h pi, a rather uniform lifetime was observed in almost the entire mice including the tumor (Balb/c mice: 747 ± 15 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: 740 ± 5 ps); except in the abdomen at the level of the intestines (Balb/c mice: 602 ± 18 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: 608 ± 27 ps) and liver (Balb/c mice: 683 ± 17 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: 654 ± 11) (Fig. 3(c), 3(g)). Therefore, FL contrast between the tumor and excretion organs was already present at this time point. Between 1 h and 24 h pi, an increase in average lifetime values of 50-80 ps was observed in local intestinal segments of all mice (Fig. 3(c), 3(g); Fig. S5): although FL contrast between tumor (t) and intestines (i) remained, FL differences between those tissues decreased up to 24 h pi (Balb/c mice: $\Delta_{1h-t\&i}$: 146 ± 27 ps; $\Delta_{6h-t\&i}$: 90 ± 32 ps; $\Delta_{24h-t\&i}$: 55 ± 23 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: $\Delta_{1h-t\&i}$: 133 ± 22 ps; $\Delta_{6h-t\&i}$: 112 ± 32 ps; $\Delta_{24h-t\&i}$: 74 ± 9 ps). Meanwhile, the average lifetime in the tumor remained relatively stable (Balb/c mice: \bar{x}_{1h-t} 747 ± 15 ps; \bar{x}_{6h-t} 726 ± 11 ps; \bar{x}_{24h-t} 726 ± 5 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: \bar{x}_{1h-t} 740 ± 5 ps; \bar{x}_{6h-t} 740 ± 22 ps; \bar{x}_{24h-t} 742 ± 21 ps) (Fig. 3(c), 3(g)). In all other regions, such as in tissue surrounding the tumor (st), lifetime values decreased as time progressed (Balb/c mice: \bar{x}_{1h-st} 749 ± 12 ps; \bar{x}_{6h-st} 716 ± 9 ps; \bar{x}_{24h-st} 662 ± 13 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: \bar{x}_{1h-st} 740 ± 11 ps; \bar{x}_{6h-st} 700 ± 19 ps; \bar{x}_{24h-st} 656 ± 40 ps) (Fig. 3(c), 3(g)). Only by 24 h pi, a clear contrast ($\Delta_{t\&st} \geq 60$ ps) between tumor and surrounding tissue emerged (Balb/c mice: $\Delta_{1h-t\&st}$: -2 ± 10 ps; $\Delta_{6h-t\&st}$: 10 ± 2 ps; $\Delta_{24h-t\&st}$: 64 ± 13 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: $\Delta_{1h-t\&st}$: 0.5 ± 11 ps; $\Delta_{6h-t\&st}$: 40 ± 8 ps; $\Delta_{24h-t\&st}$: 86 ± 20 ps). By 48 h pi, when most ICG had been excreted and fluorescence remained mainly localized at the level of the tumor, the largest contrast between tumor and surrounding tissue was observed for both mouse strains (Balb/c mice: $\Delta_{48h-t\&st}$ 109 ± 25 ps; C57Bl/6J $\Delta_{48h-t\&st}$ 96 ± 22 ps), indicating that the optimal imaging time point for FLI remains 24-48 h pi of ICG. By 48 h pi, the average lifetime values in the intestines (Balb/c mice: 595 ± 64 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: 497 ± 46 ps) and liver (Balb/c mice: 448 ± 67 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: 462 ± 7 ps) had decreased to baseline values similarly to what was observed at 1 h pi. Interestingly, in one Balb/c mouse lifetime values in the intestines remained larger (667 ps) over time (Fig. 4(b)-(c)). Those elevated lifetime values could also be observed in the jejunum *in situ* after euthanasia, when the abdomen had been opened, and after dissection *ex vivo* (Supplement 1, Fig. S4). Additional histopathologic analysis revealed that this segment of the intestines did not contain cancer cells, but mucus.

Ex vivo 48 h pi, FL contrast between tumor, surrounding tissue and organs was preserved, although FI values decreased in all tissues after dissection. In all mice but one balb/c mouse, the tumor had retained the largest lifetime value compared to tissue surrounding the tumor, liver, stomach, intestines and kidneys (Fig. 3(a), 3(e)).

3.4. Intensity- and lifetime values of ICG are altered in formalin-fixed paraffin blocks

To evaluate whether paraffin embedded tissue could be used to confirm our macroscopic measurements on a microscopic level, HDR images of paraffin blocks were acquired two weeks post-embedding. Paraffin blocks of all tissues (tumor, liver and intestinal tissue) imaged with the *tau*CAM camera revealed a decrease in FI values for the tumor (t) (Balb/c mouse (n = 1): Δ_t 8342 AU; C57Bl/6J (n = 3): Δ_t -5154 ± 7446) and intestinal (i) tissue (Balb/c mouse (n = 1): Δ_i -4196 AU; C57Bl/6J (n = 3): Δ_i -2151 ± 385 AU) as compared to the FI of freshly excised tissue. For the FFPE blocks with liver (l) tissue, FI values had clearly decreased for the Balb/c mouse ($\Delta_l \approx -3268$ AU) whereas only slight differences were observed for the C57Bl/6J mice (Δ_l 143.25 ± 641.70) (Supplement 1, Fig. S5). In contrast to the FI measurements, an increase in FL values of both the tumor (Balb/c mouse (n = 1): Δ_t 293 ps; C57Bl/6J mice (n = 3): Δ_t 210 ± 96 ps) and liver (Balb/c mouse (n = 1): Δ_l 296 ps; C57Bl/6J mice (n = 3): Δ_l 274 ± 56 ps)

were observed compared to values observed *ex vivo* 48 h pi while FL differences between tissue types became slightly smaller (Supplement 1, Fig. S5). In paraffin blocks with intestinal tissue, insufficient FI values were present for reliable FL measurements and therefore no FL values of those FFPE intestinal tissue blocks were presented on the HDR FLI plot. The resulting FL values obtained in FFPE blocks of tumor and liver were evaluated with FLIM but had insufficient signal-to-noise ratios for reliable pixel-by-pixel FL computation and were therefore not further investigated on a microscopic scale.

4. Discussion

The current study is the first to report the FLI time-course of ICG *in vivo*. Two immune-competent mouse models were used to ensure robustness of results. Although FL measurements are considered dependent on the molecular environment of a fluorophore, the optimal FLI time point for tumor identification using the non-targeting near-infrared dye ICG deems similar as for FI imaging, 24-48 h pi. However, earlier time points (i.e., 1 h pi) might be of interest to investigate for certain tumor types (i.e., intestinal- and liver tumors).

Consistent with previous studies in tumor-bearing mice receiving 5 mg/kg ICG [31,32], peak FI values were observed in all tissues at 1 h pi followed by a decline in all tissues over time. Since healthy tissue is known to have faster elimination rates of ICG than tumor tissue [32], TBRs increased over time. FL contrast between tumor and surrounding tissue only emerged between 6 h and 24 h pi. The largest contrast was observed by 24-48 h pi when TBRs ≥ 2 were observed. In human specimens evaluated macroscopically by *Pal. et al. (2023)*, reported FL values of macroscopic measurements were largest in a head and neck tumor specimen (liposarcoma: 720 ps; myxofibrosarcoma 730 ps; normal adjacent muscle: 440 ps), followed by a liver tumor specimen (hepatocellular carcinoma: 650 ps; surrounding tissue: 520 ps) and an intestinal tumor specimen (metastatic colon carcinoma: 620 ps; surrounding tissue 540 ps) [7]. In that study, the patients from which those specimens were resected had received ICG 20-72 h prior to surgery (ICG dose not mentioned). The average FL differences between tumor and surrounding tissue of those specimens were 280 ps, 290 ps, 130 ps and 80 ps respectively [7]. In our *in vivo* study, similar FL differences up to 134 ps were observed (Balb/c mice: $\Delta_{24h-t\&st}$: 64 ± 13 ps; $\Delta_{48h-t\&st}$ 109 ± 25 ps; C57Bl/6J mice: $\Delta_{24h-t\&st}$: 86 ± 20 ps; $\Delta_{48h-t\&st}$ 96 ± 22 ps). Further studies are required to determine which magnitude of FL differences can meaningfully discriminate tumor from healthy tissue during surgical procedures.

Although we did not investigate the underlying causes for FLI contrast between tumor and surrounding tissue, it is known that the FL of ICG increases in the presence of serum proteins [7]. Following iv administration, ICG rapidly binds to plasma proteins, predominantly lipoproteins (LPs), generating ICG-LP complexes [33]. In tumors, ICG-LP complexes can bind exposed hydrophobic phospholipid tails in cell membranes caused by necrosis, possibly preventing degradation. In contrast, in vital tumor tissue, defective lymphatic drainage triggered by the enhanced permeability and retention effect triggers the prolonged presence of ICG [33]; it remains unknown whether ICG remains protein-bound in those settings. When ICG is cleared from healthy tissue but remains protein-bound in tumor tissue, this could in part clarify why contrast only emerged from 24 h onwards. The extent of the effect of fluorescent scattered light from a primary tumor onto surrounding tissue and its influence on FLI contrast however remain to be investigated. By 1 h and 6 h pi, higher FI levels were observed in intestinal tissue of Balb/c mice compared to C57Bl/6J mice but similar FL values were observed in the intestines of both mouse strains. Whether the shorter FL observed in the intestines (Balb/c mice: $\approx 602 \pm 18$ ps; C57Bl/6J mice: $\approx 607 \pm 27$ ps) 1 h post-injection of ICG is of benefit in the resection of intestinal tumors requires further investigation. In all mice, an increase in average FL values in the intestines was observed by 24 h pi but only in one balb/c mouse, in the jejunum, this larger FL had remained up to 48 h pi *in vivo* and *ex vivo*. Histopathology revealed no tumorigenic neoplastic characteristics

but a rather large amount of mucus which may have interfered with the elimination of ICG. Since mucus contains proteins and proteins increase the lifetime of ICG, this may have triggered a higher lifetime at 48 h pi *in vivo*, *in situ* and *ex vivo*. Similarly, it would likewise be valuable to explore whether measurements at 1 h pi are of relevance for liver tumor demarcation. Our imaging was conducted through the intact abdominal wall. This differs from surgical settings where the abdominal cavity is opened.

Tumor, liver and intestinal tissue of all C57Bl/6J mice and one Balb/c mouse were processed into paraffin blocks and macroscopically imaged with the *tau*CAM camera but average FL values had already changed in all embedded tissue samples two weeks post-embedding, compared to values observed *in vivo*. In paraffin-embedded tissue, where the environment had changed, the average lifetime value of both tumor and liver increased, in contrast to measurements *in vivo* at the level of the liver where lifetime values decreased as time passed by. Similarly, Pal *et al.* (2023) observed larger FL values in FFPE tissue imaged microscopically compared to macroscopic measurements on resected tumor specimens [7]. Our study was not designed to evaluate whether average FL differences between tissues remain after paraffinization and for how long. While tissue sections were imaged microscopically using FLIM, signal-to-noise ratios in individual pixels were insufficient for reliable FLI measurements using time-correlated single photon counting FLIM [34]. However, even when sufficient signal-to-noise ratios in individual pixels would have been present, and the lifetime differences between these tissues had remained consistent across both modalities, direct comparisons between macroscopic and microscopic measurements would still be challenging. For comparisons between macroscopic and microscopic data, images are preferably analyzed in a similar manner. However, microscopic FL values are typically derived using a global fitting approach rather than fitting the decay curve at each pixel independently. Although this approach reduces analysis time, it assumes fixed lifetime values with spatially invariable contributions of each fluorescent species in the image [35,36]. In heterogeneous tissues with distinct molecular environments, such assumptions may introduce bias, especially when the true FL components are not known *a priori*. While frequency-domain algorithms allow for fast fit-free FL image analysis, those measurements are typically affected by tissue depth in turbid media [37]. Consequently, direct comparisons between macro- and microscopic FLI data are difficult. While decay curves in microscopic data can be fitted pixel-by-pixel, low signal-to-noise ratios in those pixels can introduce substantial uncertainty in the calculated FL values [35]. Possibly, making the *tau*CAM compatible with a microscopy platform; by including an objective lens with high magnification and numerical aperture, condenser lens to control the illumination for microscopic measurements and a tube lens to form the corrected image onto the camera sensor, together with proper alignment and synchronized illumination, microscopic imaging could be enabled on the same camera system with similar algorithms as those used for macroscopic measurements.

Future studies are warranted to evaluate how factors such as fixative type, fixation duration, and storage time influence FL image measurements in FFPE tissues as well as in frozen tissues. Moreover, when sufficient FI signal in FFPE tissue and/or frozen tissue is maintained, it would be worthwhile to investigate how microscopic or physical factors (e.g., optical properties and light-tissue interactions) affect the data to determine whether FLIM measurements can be reliably extrapolated to the macroscopic scale.

In mice, FL measurements provided a rather uniform lifetime over the entire tumor in mice, thereby enabling tumor identification with higher accuracy than FI measurements. However, our current study design did not allow to evaluate the accuracy of FL-based tumor delineation with ICG. In this experiment, ROIs were drawn on brightfield images based on the visible macroscopic tumor and tissue surrounding the tumor with no confirmation regarding tissue origin. Although currently implemented, FLI overlaid on color video was not available at the time of data collection, preventing the ability for targeted biopsies based on the observed FL

values *in vivo*. Therefore, the accuracy of the technique could not be evaluated *in vivo* nor *ex vivo*. However, even with FL measurements overlaid on RGB video, further research such as research on 3D imaging and reconstruction algorithms remains valuable to separate FI and FL values originating from superficial versus deep tissue layers and to discriminate true fluorescent signals from reflected or scattered light. Together with continued research on higher-resolution cameras and dedicated software for real-time FLI, future work should enable a more precise determination of the sensitivity and specificity of macroscopic FL-based tumor identification.

In this study, HDR images were generated for reliable time-domain FI and FL image analysis. All imaging systems have a linear range in which the output of signal is directly proportional to input. We previously demonstrated that the 128×128 pixel-CMOS *tauCAM* camera has a linear range between 0-15000 AU [28]. For accurate fluorescence image analysis, the relative number of photons per pixel needs to fall within this linear range as well as exceed an intrinsic pixel noise level inherent to the imaging system. However, for FL calculation not only the linearity of imaging system should be taken into account but also the quality of fluorescent decays in each pixel. When noisy and saturated pixel decay profiles are included in the calculation of average lifetime values, curve-fitting algorithms are unable to provide reliable results. To overcome this, we computed average lifetime values including only pixels in the linear range of the *tauCAM* camera with a minimum threshold of 1000 AU. A higher standard deviation in average lifetime values was observed when invalid (< 1000 AU, > 15000 AU) pixels were included compared to calculations with pixels in the linear range of 1000-15000 AU only. The HDR images provide users with the ability to calculate more reliable FI and FL values, in comparison to non-HDR images, without the need to check images for signal levels or saturation. However, in this experiment, we did not verify the decay quality of every pixel. Since motion (e.g., breathing patterns) can alter the quality of fluorescent decays, the development of algorithms or artificial intelligence tools for motion detection and compensation during time-domain FLI measurements could be worthwhile. Together with the HDR imaging approach, this would allow for even more robust and reliable time-domain FL image analysis. With this HDR imaging modus, a single HDR acquisition is performed which allows for shorter imaging times than when multiple acquisition times are measured separately: each camera pixel is read out multiple times during a single image acquisition time to create a multi-exposure (MEX) read out [28]. The multi-exposure HDR image extends the dynamic range of fluorescent images beyond 100 dB surpassing the typical dynamic range of 90 dB in macroscopic commercial FI imaging systems [28,38]. Similar HDR measurements have already proven highly effective in radiography, laser scanning fluorescence intensity microscopy and CCD-based fluorescence intensity computed tomography where contrast between tissues is enhanced both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* [29]. In those FI studies, a minimum of two frames was suggested for accurate HDR FI measurements [29]. Our HDR FLI image cubes could also be generated from only two image cubes from separate acquisition times, provided the combination of these acquisition times resulted in a 100% valid pixel count for a reliable lifetime computation.

5. Conclusion

FLI with ICG holds promise to provide valuable information on tissue properties compared to FI imaging alone. However, additional studies are required to confirm the accuracy of FL-based tumor delineation with ICG. Future studies should evaluate whether the measured lifetime of ICG is affected by tissue depth and fluorescence scattering on a pixel-by-pixel level. The generation of HDR time-domain image cubes can assist in more appropriate FI and FL measurements in the time-domain.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

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